

SOCIAL WORK EDUCATION AWARENESS TOWARDS PROFESSIONALISM AMONG HISBAH CORPS: IMPLICATIONS FOR POLICY REFORMS IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate social work education awareness towards professionalism among Hisbah Corps and provides important implications for reforms in the policy that established the Hisbah Corps in Kano State, Nigeria. The study objectives are to examine the social work services provided by Hisbah Board; determine the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education; determine the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice, and determine the challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties in Kano State. The study adopted a survey research methodology over a population of 1809 clients and corps members working at Hisbah Board headquarters in Kano State. A sample of 317 was drawn based on the specifications by the krejcie and Morgan's table for determining sample size. The sampling procedure used in reaching out to the sampled subjects was through the random sampling technique. Two instruments were used for the collection of data; an interview, and a Likert Scale type questionnaire. The questionnaire was subjected to validity and reliability tests; where experts validated the contents in relation to the objectives of the study, and its reliability was obtained through the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained. While the data from the interview was analysed semantically and discussed qualitatively, the data generated through the questionnaire was analysed using descriptive statistics in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean and cumulative mean scores. Findings of the study revealed among others that the social work services provided by Hisbah Board in Kano State are public awareness campaigns and education, working with young people, dispute settlement, family mediation services, welfare activities, reconciliation of couples (Family Casework), organise counselling/provide support for inter-marriages among widows (Auren Zawarawa), repatriation and care support services for vulnerable children and families, and the challenges faced by the Hisbah Board in discharging their duties in Kano State includes interpreting and enforcing Sharia law within the framework of Nigeria's secular legal system; enforcing Islamic law and moral codes, accusations of human rights abuses, etc. The recommendations made by the study include; Kano State government should reform the policy that established Hisbah in the State, and the office of the Head of Civil Service together with the institutions offering social work programmes should provide sensitisation workshops for Hisbah corps members targeted on the awareness on social work education and professionalisation periodically.

Keywords: Academic, Social Work Education, Professionalism, Policy and Reform

Introduction

Part of the "agenda setting" in public policy formulation, planning and implementation are the consequences of social, economic and political problems that disturb the general public. Contemporarily, attempts were made by governments across developed and developing countries to formulate policies that contribute to the development of their communities in terms promotion of the general well-being of the citizenry. However, social work profession in its various forms addresses the multiple and often very complex connections between people and environments (Faruque and Ahmmmed, 2013). Social work is defined as

“a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people. Principles of social justice, human rights, collective responsibility and respect for diversities are central to social work. Underpinned by theories of social work, social sciences, humanities and indigenous knowledge, social work engages people and structures to address life challenges and enhance wellbeing.” (IFSW, 2014)

Within the professional conduct of social work, the main objective is to help people to attain their full capacities, promotes well-being and addresses dys-functionalities at various levels of their environment. Social work profession emphasises problem solving and positive change from a strength-based perspective. Social workers serve as change agents in society and in the lives of the individuals, families, and communities that they serve. Globalisation also, has brought with it demands for control, domination, power, and vested interests. Indeed, this has brought unique challenges for internationally minded social workers. Our world has become increasingly divided and decisive by class, clan, religion, race, creed, gender, and caste (Day, 2000). These power lines and divisions have resulted in much greater divides between the small minority who hold power and control and the majority who do not.

A contemporary key to social work education is the socialisation towards a professional value structure, which is an inherent part of social work education that is universally accepted and utilise by schools and institutions of social work. The “profession” social work places great emphasis on what is often termed its value competent. Social work education is focus to provide training of individuals to inculcate appropriate attitudes as well as knowledge and skills that support people in their problems ranging from individual, family and communities. Social work education awareness is an important aspect of preparing individuals for careers in the field of social work. Awareness in social work education involves understanding and promoting key principles, values, and concepts of social work practice. The profession of social work like many other professions has laid down certain expectations with regard to the quality of mind and value-orientation for those who joined it. The training could have little or no impact on the learner’s professional competence if the innate capacities and aptitudes of the learners are not in tune with the expectations of professional education for social work. (Collings, Kent and Bhavnani, 1977). In different phases, then, students of social work bring with them beliefs and attitudes compatible with the professional structure. Therefore, successful socialisation towards achieving professional goals is dependent both on selecting students open to such socialisation and on the effectiveness of the educational environment.

Social work practice in the context of Nigeria ensue from historical traditional phases handed over from generation to generation. Today, due to emancipation of modern social work which was the result of missionaries, westernisation and/or colonisation, many people have joined the profession without pursue of formal training expected for a practitioner. This has caused bubbling-issues such as whether the practice follows legal standard, professional ethics and training opportunities among practitioners. Therefore, social work education has become necessary to provide well-trained and qualified personnel that can effectively render services to individuals and families encounter different problems in their societies. Since the second world war and after the independence, Nigeria have faced various social problems that deteriorated the living conditions of its citizenry. These problems include unemployment, prostitution, destitution, rape/gender violence, divorce, unwanted-children, etc. Many States across Nigeria have established laws and policies targeted on the control of these common disturbing social vices in both urban, sub-urban and rural villages across the federation. In Kano State therefore, and with the establishment of Sharia state in 2000; some activists formed Kano Hisbah as a religious organisation run by a committee of trustees (Adamu 2008; Olaniyi 2011; Ibrahim 2020 cited in Ibrahim, 2022). In 2003, during Ibrahim Shekarau’s administration the Hisbah was transformed into a state agency by using Section 38, sub-section 1 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which stipulated that:

‘Every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom (either alone or in community with others, and in public or in private) to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice, and observance’. (Nigeria, 1999:18)

The Shekarau administration appropriated this legal provision and passed the Kano State Hisbah Law. Kano Hisbah became a government institution (Yusufari 2004) with a new name, Kano State Hisbah (KSH). The creation of KSH allowed thousands of volunteers to become public workers under the state government payroll. It led to the mass employment of people with religious training and activist backgrounds to manage the moral reform project “Hisbah Board”.

Having seen these personnel engaged in social work activities; the question ask is that, are they found suitable in terms of knowledge, skill and expertise to undertake social work practice? Have they attended any formal training or educational exercise? And do they have first class information on the awareness of social work education viz; schools, training, professional body and many more? It is based on this background that this study assesses the Social Work Education Awareness towards Professionalism among Hisbah Corps and draws its implications for Policy Reforms in Kano State, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Despite the KSH Law described “Yan Hisbah” as a Justice of Peace Corps (Olaniyi 2009), which is recognised as a civil group in the secular constitution. This law also mandated the Board to employ and train its “Corps” members to actively participate in the provision of various services that reduce the hardship around the living conditions of vulnerable sections in Kano State. These vulnerable populations in the state include women (Widows and Divorced), children, youth, displaced families, families in disputes, neighbours, etc. in his work, Ibrahim (2022) reported that the Board has among its corps members ‘Ulamas’ (Islamic scholars), health workers, carpenters, auto mechanics, technicians, and people from other different professions. Ibrahim, added that the Corps members have different educational qualifications, including academic degrees, alarammomi (those who memorized Quran by heart), and Malamai (Ulama) and madrassah teachers), learned in various Islamic fields. What brings these people together as Yan Hisbah, is their commitment to implement Sharia reforms.

Unlike today, which they are seeing engaging in various social work activities that deal with vulnerable segments of the people in Kano State. Several reforms and innovations imposed the power of the Hisbah to have the authority to arrest and prosecute people in Kano State. Apart from protection of child right in case of divorce among couples, the Judges (AlKalai) have the power to collect and hand-over money and properties to widows and/or divorced women in the State. It is in the light of the forgoing discourse that this study intends to assess the social work education awareness towards professionalism among Hisbah Corps and draw its implication for policy reforms in Kano State, Nigeria

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to assess the social work education awareness towards professionalism among Hisbah Corps and draw its implications for policy reforms in Kano State, other objectives of the study were:

- i. To examine the social work services provided by Hisbah Board in Kano State;
- ii. To determine the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education in Kano State;
- iii. To determine the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State, and
- iv. To determine the challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties in Kano State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

- i. What are the social work services provided by Hisbah Board in Kano State?
- ii. What is the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education in Kano State?
- iii. What is the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State?
- iv. What are the challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties in Kano State?

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research methodology over a population of 1809 clients and corps members working at Hisbah Board headquarters in Kano State. A sample of 317 was drawn based on the specifications by the krejcie and Morgan’s table for determining sample size. The sampling procedure used in the study

was a purposive sampling technique where 10% of the sample was allocated to clients as proposed by Gay and Anderson (1970), which stipulated that for the conduct of an interview; 10% of the sampled subjects can be representative of the sample in a study. The rest of 285 was allocated to Corps working at various Hisbah units in Kano State Board Headquarters. However, in reaching out to the sampled subjects, a simple random sampling technique was used. Two instruments were used for the collection of data; an interview, and a Likert Scale type questionnaire. The questionnaire was subjected to validity and reliability tests; where experts validated the contents in relation to the objectives of the study, and its reliability was obtained through the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained. While the data from the interview was reported in semantic and discussed qualitatively, the data generated through the questionnaire was analysed using descriptive statistics in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean and cumulative mean score. These was obtained by rateing SA=4, A=3, D=2 and SD=1; therefore, $4+3+2+1=10/4=2.5$. these means that the decision rule in this study was based on mean and cumulative mean score of 2.50 and above that indicates the acceptance of statements of items in the questionnaire. However, any mean and cumulative score below 2.50 indicates that statements of items in the questionnaire were rejected. Also, in determining the level of awareness the researcher used high (H), medium (M) and low (L).

Results

Research question 1. What are the social work services provided by Hisbah Board in Kano State?

Table 1 Social Work Services Provided by Hisbah Board in Kano State

The social work services provided by Hisbah	SA		A		D		SD		\bar{X}	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
engages in public awareness campaigns and education	63	22.3	107	37.8	71	25.1	42	14.8	2.67	Accepted
works with young people, providing guidance and counseling to steer them away from behaviours and activities	49	17.3	96	33.9	87	30.7	51	18.0	2.50	Accepted
dispute settlement between people engage e.g. business, land-lord and tenant, employee and employer etc.	83	29.3	91	32.2	87	30.7	22	7.8	2.83	Accepted
offer family mediation services to help resolve disputes within families or communities	73	25.8	81	28.6	104	36.7	25	8.8	2.71	Accepted
engage in welfare activities, such as distributing food, rent, medical bills, etc to the needy	99	35.0	126	44.5	47	16.6	11	3.9	3.10	Accepted
reconciliation of couples to control divorce and provide alternative for child care. (Family Casework)	59	20.8	86	30.4	109	38.5	29	10.2	2.61	Accepted
organise counselling, provide support for inter-marriages among widows. (Auren Zawarawa)	129	45.6	131	46.3	22	7.8	1	0.4	3.37	Accepted
repatriation of lost and found persons to their various places of origin/destinations	102	36.0	91	32.2	72	25.4	18	6.4	2.97	Accepted
provide care support services for vulnerable children and families	85	30.0	82	29.0	60	21.2	56	19.8	2.69	Accepted

Cumulative mean = 2.83

Above Table 1 describes social work services provided by Hisbah Board in Kano State. According to the table, respondents with highest percentage of 37.8 (102) agreed with the statement that Hisbah engages in public awareness campaigns and education efforts to inform residents about the principles of Sharia law and encourage adherence to Islamic morality. The mean of 2.67 indicates that this statement was accepted.

Regarding the statements that Hisbah often works with young people, providing guidance and counseling to steer them away from behaviours and activities that go against Islamic principles, 96 (33.9%) of the respondents agreed with the said statement. The mean score of 2.50 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents. In addition to this, sound percentage of 32.2 (91) agreed with the statement that Hisbah engaged in dispute settlement between people e.g. business, land-lord and tenant, employee and employer etc. The mean score of 2.83 indicates that this statement was accepted. In another statement that Hisbah offer family mediation services to help resolve disputes within families or communities, often using Islamic principles as a basis for conflict resolution. The highest percentage of 36.7 (104) disagreed with the said statement. The mean score of 2.71 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents.

Furthermore, the highest percentage of 44.5 (126) of the respondents agreed with the statement that Hisbah engage in welfare activities, such as distributing food, rent, medical bills, etc to the needy. Here, a strong mean score of 3.10 indicates that the statement was greatly accepted by the respondents. Also, the sound percentage of 38.5 (109) disagreed with the statement that Hisbah engage in reconciliation of couples to control divorce and provide alternative for child care. (Family Casework). The mean score 2.61 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents. Complement to this, the highest percentage 45.6 (129) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah engage in organise counselling, provide support for inter-marriages among widows (Auren Zawarawa). Here also, sound mean score 3.37 indicates that the statement that Hisbah engage in organise counselling, provide support for inter-marriages among widows (Auren Zawarawa) was highly accepted by the respondents.

Within this Table, the respondents who strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah provide care support services for vulnerable children and families constituted the highest percentage of 30 (85). The mean score of 2.69 indicates that this statement was accepted. Finally, it is observed that the cumulative mean score of 2.83 justifies that the statements of items in the questionnaire were considered accepted by the respondents.

Research Question 2. What is the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education in Kano State?

Table 2 Level of Awareness of the Hisbah Corps on Social Work Education

Level of Awareness of the Hisbah Corps on Social Work Education	H		M		L		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
S W students and professionals should demonstrate a strong awareness of the core values of S W	51	18.0	66	23.3	166	58.6	Low
Awareness in SWE includes an understanding of the various social systems and institutions e.g, families, schools,	76	26.9	72	25.4	135	47.7	Low
S W students should be aware of cultural diversity and possess the knowledge and skills necessary to work effectively with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.	70	24.7	77	27.2	136	48.1	Low
SWE should raise awareness of social injustices, including issues related to poverty, discrimination, inequality, etc	72	25.4	63	22.3	148	52.3	Low
S W students should be able to demonstrate empathy and engage empathetic listening with clients and communities.	51	18.0	90	31.8	142	50.1	Low
SWE should promote critical thinking skills, encouraging students to analyze complex social issues	93	32.9	78	27.6	112	39.5	Low
Awareness includes familiarity with various theoretical frameworks in S W, e.g. systems theory, strengths-based perspective, etc	67	23.7	79	27.9	137	48.4	Low

S W students should be aware of relevant legislation, policies, and regulations that impact S W practice, e.g. child welfare laws	73	25.8	74	26.1	136	48.1	Low
An essential aspect of SWE is self-awareness.	74	26.1	68	24.0	141	49.8	Low
SWE should equip students with the skills to make ethical decisions in challenging situations	75	26.5	79	27.9	129	45.6	Low
S W students should be aware of the importance of collaborating with professionals from other disciplines, e.g. psychology, medicine, edu. to provide holistic care and support.	63	22.3	70	24.7	150	53.0	Low
awareness is the practice of reflection, where S W students and professionals regularly evaluate their actions, decisions, and outcomes to improve their practice.	71	25.1	81	28.6	131	46.3	Low
S W students should be encouraged to engage local communities for community-based initiatives.	69	24.4	66	23.3	148	52.3	Low

From the above Table 2 on the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education, the highest percentage 58.6 (166) agreed with the statement that the level of awareness on social work students and professionals should demonstrate a strong awareness of the core values of social work, including service, social justice, dignity and worth of the person, importance of human relationships, integrity, and competence was low. However, the highest percentage 47.7 (135) of the respondents opined that the statement that the level of awareness on social work education includes an understanding of the various social systems and institutions that impact individuals and communities, such as families, schools, healthcare, and the criminal justice system was low. Moreover, the highest 136 (48.1%) of the respondents believed the statement that the level of awareness on social work students should be aware of cultural diversity and possess the knowledge and skills necessary to work effectively with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds was low. However, the highest percentage 52.3 (148) of the respondents agreed that the statement that the level of awareness on social work education should raise awareness of social injustices, including issues related to poverty, discrimination, inequality, and systemic oppression was low. Also, the highest percentage 50.1 (142) of the respondents agreed that the statement that the level of awareness on social work students should be able to demonstrate empathy and engage in empathetic listening with clients and communities was low. However, the highest percentage 39.5 (112) of the respondents believed that the statement that the level of awareness on social work education should promote critical thinking skills, encouraging students to analyze complex social issues and develop effective strategies for addressing them was low. Added to this, the highest percentage 48.4 (137) of the respondents agreed that the statement that the level of awareness includes familiarity with various theoretical frameworks in social work, such as systems theory, ecological perspective, strengths-based perspective, and person-in-environment perspective was low.

This Table also indicates, the sound percentage 48.1 (136) of the respondents opined that the statement that the level of awareness on social work students should be aware of relevant legislation, policies, and regulations that impact social work practice, such as child welfare laws, healthcare policies, and disability rights was low. Similarly, the highest percentages 49.8 (141) of the respondents believed that the statement that the level of awareness on essential aspect of social work education is self-awareness; students should be aware of their own values, biases, and limitations and how these can impact their practice was low. Furthermore, 129 (45.6%) of the respondents agreed that the statement that the level of awareness on social work education should equip students with the skills to make ethical decisions in challenging situations, balancing the best interests of clients with ethical principles was low. However, the highest percentage 53 (150) opined that the statement that the level of awareness on social work students should be aware of the importance of collaborating with professionals from other disciplines, such as psychology, medicine, and education, to provide holistic care and support was low. Complement to this, reasonable percentage of 46.3 (131) of the respondents agreed that the statement that the level of awareness on awareness is the practice of

reflection, where social work students and professionals regularly evaluate their actions, decisions, and outcomes to improve their practice was low. However, the highest percentage 54.3 (148) of the respondents believed that the statement that the level of awareness on social work students should be encouraged to engage with their local communities, understanding community dynamics and involving themselves in community-based initiatives was low. The above interpretations indicate that the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education in Kano State is low.

Research Question 3. What is the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State?

Table 3 Level of Awareness of the Hisbah Corps on Professional Social Work Practice

Level Awareness of the Hisbah Corps on Professional Social Work Practice	H		M		L		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
S W adhere to a professional code of ethics that outlines their commitment to promoting the well-being of individuals, families, and communities	63	22.3	71	25.1	149	52.6	Low
S W are dedicated to advancing social justice and addressing systemic inequalities and injustices.	57	20.1	82	29.0	144	50.9	Low
S W empower clients by helping them build on their strengths, develop their abilities, and make informed decisions.	71	25.1	78	27.6	134	47.3	Low
S W focus on the needs and goals of their clients. They engage in active listening, empathy, and collaboration to help clients identify and achieve their objectives.	64	22.6	70	24.7	149	52.7	Low
S. work takes a holistic view of clients' lives, considering not only their immediate challenges but also their social, cultural, economic, and environmental contexts.	76	26.9	86	30.4	121	42.7	Low
S W often act as advocates for their clients, advocating for their rights, needs, and access to services within various systems and institutions.	70	24.7	65	23.0	148	52.3	Low
S W are required to maintain high levels of professional competence through ongoing education, training, and supervision to ensure they provide effective and evidence-based services.	63	22.3	66	23.3	154	54.4	Low
S W are bound by strict confidentiality guidelines to protect the privacy of their clients	68	24.0	73	25.8	142	50.3	Low
S W are culturally competent and strive to provide services that are sensitive and responsive to the diverse cultural backgrounds and identities of their clients.	62	21.9	78	27.6	143	50.5	Low
S W analyse and understand how social systems and institutions impact individuals and communities	72	25.4	61	21.6	150	53.0	Low
S W typically hold a degree in social work (BSW, MSW, or PhD) and often need to be licensed or certified to practice	65	23.0	72	25.4	146	51.6	Low
S W engage in lifelong learning and professional development to stay updated on emerging issues, research, and best practices in the field.	69	24.4	82	29.0	132	46.7	Low
S W often collaborate with professionals from other disciplines, such as psychology, medicine, education, and law, to provide comprehensive services to clients.	71	25.1	74	26.1	138	48.7	Low

The above Table 3 describes the awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State. According to the Table, highest percentage 52.6 (149) of the respondents believed that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers adhere to a professional code of ethics that outlines their commitment to promoting the well-being of individuals, families, and communities was low. Similarly, the highest percentage 50.9 (144) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that

social workers are dedicated to advancing social justice and addressing systemic inequalities and injustices was low. However, the highest percentage 47.3 (134) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers empower clients by helping them build on their strengths, develop their abilities, and make informed decisions was low. Contrary to this, the highest percentage of 52.7 (149) of the respondents opined that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers focus on the needs and goals of their clients was low. Moreover, highest percentage of 54.4 (154) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that social work takes a holistic view of clients' lives, considering not only their immediate challenges but also their social, cultural, economic, and environmental contexts was low. Contrary to this, is the highest percentage 52.3 (148) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that social work often acts as advocates for their clients, advocating for their rights, needs, and access to services within various systems and institutions was low.

This Table also highlights that highest percentage 54.4 (154) of the respondents opined that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers are required to maintain high levels of professional competence through ongoing education, training, and supervision to ensure they provide effective and evidence-based services was low. Complement to this, the highest percentages 50.3 (142) agreed that the statement that social workers are bound by strict confidentiality guidelines to protect the privacy of their clients, except in cases where there is a legal duty to disclose or a risk of harm to the client or others was low. Added to this was the highest percentage 50.5 (143) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers are culturally competent and strive to provide services that are sensitive and responsive to the diverse cultural backgrounds and identities of their clients was low. Similarly, the highest percentage 53 (150) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers analyse and understand how social systems and institutions impact individuals and communities was low. In addition to this, were those 146 (51.6%) of the respondents believed that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers typically hold a degree in social work (BSW, MSW, or PhD) and often need to be licensed or certified to practice, depending on the jurisdiction and the specific area of practice was low. However, highest percentage 46.7 (132) of the respondents agreed that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers engage in lifelong learning and professional development to stay updated on emerging issues, research, and best practices in the field was low. Similarly, the highest percentage 48.7 (138) of the respondents opined that the statement on the level of awareness that social workers often collaborate with professionals from other disciplines, such as psychology, medicine, education, and law, to provide comprehensive services to clients was low. From the above interpretations, it indicates that the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State is low.

Research Question 4. What are the challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties in Kano State?

Table 4. The challenges Faced by the Hisbah Corps in Discharging their Duties

Hisbah Corps face challenge	SA		A		D		SD		\bar{X}	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
in interpreting and enforcing Sharia law within the framework of Nigeria's secular legal system.	79	27.9	75	26.5	69	24.4	60	21.2	2.61	Accepted
by enforcing Islamic law and moral codes, which may not align with the views and beliefs of all residents in Kano State.	85	30.0	61	21.6	68	24.0	69	24.4	2.57	Accepted
in accusations of human rights abuses, such as arbitrary arrests, harassment, and public floggings, which violate the rights and freedoms of individuals	93	32.9	75	26.5	65	23.0	50	17.7	2.74	Accepted
on enforcing conservative interpretations of Islamic morality, which can lead to gender imbalances and discrimination.	76	26.9	62	21.9	73	25.8	72	25.4	2.50	Accepted
in public opposition: Some people with more liberal or secular views, may resist their efforts and view their activities as oppressive or intrusive, and can lead to social tensions and unrest.	83	29.3	76	26.9	64	22.6	60	21.2	2.64	Accepted
of inadequate funding which can limit their effectiveness in carrying out their duties.	84	29.7	64	22.6	76	26.9	59	20.8	2.61	Accepted
of inadequate professional staffing which can limit their effectiveness in carrying out their duties.	72	25.4	78	27.6	66	23.3	67	23.7	2.54	Accepted
in sometimes be influenced by political leaders or factions, which may compromise their ability to carry out their duties impartially and in accordance with the rule of law.	75	26.5	90	31.8	60	21.2	58	20.5	2.61	Accepted
in collaboration and coordination with other law enforcement agencies in the state especially when their mandates and approaches differ.	69	24.4	83	29.3	71	25.1	60	21.2	2.57	Accepted
Cumulative mean = 2.60										

The above Table 4 indicates the challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties in Kano State. According to the Table, highest percentage 27.9 (79) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps face challenges in interpreting and enforcing Sharia law within the framework of Nigeria's secular legal system. The mean score of 2.61 indicates that this statement was accepted by the

respondents. In addition to this, the highest percentage 30 (85) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps primarily enforces Islamic law and moral codes, which may not align with the views and beliefs of all residents in Kano State. This limited jurisdiction can lead to tensions and conflicts within the diverse population of the state. The mean score of 2.57 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents. Furthermore, sound percentage 32.9 (93) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps has faced accusations of human rights abuses, such as arbitrary arrests, harassment, and public floggings, which violate the rights and freedoms of individuals. These allegations have drawn criticism from human rights organizations and activists. The mean score of 2.74 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents. Similarly, highest percentage 26.9 (76) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps often focuses on enforcing conservative interpretations of Islamic morality, which can lead to gender imbalances and discrimination. Women may face stricter regulations and limitations on their freedom and choices, which has been a point of contention. The mean score of 2.50 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents.

Furthermore, highest percentage 29.3 (83) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps face challenge with public opposition: Some segments of the population, particularly those with more liberal or secular views, may resist the efforts of the Hisbah Corps and view their activities as oppressive or intrusive. This can lead to social tensions and unrest. The mean score of 2.64 indicate that this statement was accepted by the respondents. However, highest percentage of 29.7 (84) of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps face challenge of inadequate funding which can limit their effectiveness in carrying out their duties. The mean score of 2.61 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents. Similarly, highest percentage 27.6 (78) of the respondents agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps face challenge of inadequate professional staffing which can limit their effectiveness in carrying out their duties. The mean score of 2.54 indicate that this statement was accepted by the respondents. However, highest percentage 31.8 (90) of the respondents agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps face challenge with political interference; in sometimes be influenced by political leaders or factions, which may compromise their ability to carry out their duties impartially and in accordance with the rule of law. The mean score of 2.61 indicates that this statement was accepted by the respondents. Complement to this, highest percentage of 29.3 (83) of the respondents agreed with the statement that Hisbah Corps face challenge in collaboration and coordination with other law enforcement agencies in the state especially when their mandates and approaches differ. These statement of items in the questionnaire were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.60 higher than the decision rule 2.50.

Findings

From the foregoing data analysis, the following findings were deduced:

- i. The social work services provided by the Hisbah Board in Kano State are public awareness campaigns and education, working with young people, dispute settlement, family mediation services, welfare activities, reconciliation of couples (Family Casework), organise counselling/provide support for inter-marriages among widows (Auren Zawarawa), repatriation and care support services for vulnerable children and families.
- ii. The level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education in Kano State was low.
- iii. The level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State was low.
- iv. The challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties are interpreting and enforcing Sharia law within the framework of Nigeria's secular legal system; enforcing Islamic law and moral codes, which may not align with the views and beliefs of all residents; accusations of human rights abuses; enforcing conservative interpretations of Islamic morality; public opposition; inadequate funding; inadequate professional staffing; influenced by political leaders or factions, and collaboration and coordination with other law enforcement agencies in Kano State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of this study which revealed that the social work services provided by the Hisbah Board in Kano State are public awareness campaigns and education, working with young people (Youth Work), dispute settlement, family mediation services, welfare activities, reconciliation of couples (Family

Casework), organise counselling/provide support for inter-marriages among widows (Auren Zawarawa), repatriation and care support services for vulnerable children and families. This finding relates with the interview conducted with the various clients that benefited from the services of Hisbah Board in Kano State. Thus:

“Women and men (Spouses) received counselling services in relation to pre-marriage period, during divorce and alternative care-services for children after the death of one of the spouses. Neighbourhood reconciliation also was carried-out effectively and so many youths have benefitted from youth education and enlightenment programmes targeted on reduction/eradication of drug abuse/trafficking, filming, prostitution, political-thuggery and phone-snatching.”

In a study entitled *Counseling Services in Muslim Communal Life in Malaysia* by Zainab, Wan-Ibrahim and Asyraf (2014); the objectives of the study were achieved using a content analysis design, the data indicates that the counseling service has existed since the era of the Prophet Muhammad which was known as “nasihah”. During Saiyidina Umar al-Khattab’s era, he had established the so called “Diwan al-Hisbah” as the first step towards upgrading nasihah as a profession in regards to the missionary program and has been part of the approaches for missionary activities within the Islamic Religious Department of the country. The service among which include helping couples experiencing domestic conflict and providing necessary assistance to re-establish mutual understanding and strengthen their family ties and relations. Added to this is the study conducted by Abdulhamid and Sanusi (2016) entitled *Challenges and Negative Effects of Divorce among Muslim Women in Northern Nigeria*. Both primary and secondary sources for the work which comprised of Qur’an, Hadith and other literatures. Thus, using descriptive and analytical methods, the interprets Islamic teachings with a view to extending Islamic solutions on them. The study revealed that the challenges and negative effects of divorce are usually much stronger on the woman and her off-spring than the man. These ranges from psychological trauma, immoral behaviour, economic hardship, denial of custody, etc. The study recommends among other things, that parents of intending spouses should endeavor to find out the level of Islamic knowledge, habit, and character of suitors/wives to be, prior to the marriage in order to prepare adequately for a successful association. These has justified the role Hisbah played in concentrating on marriage counselling because whenever the basic social institution (family) becomes morally, psychologically and economically healthy a good community and society will be maintained.

However, regarding the second finding of this study which discovered that the level of awareness of the Hisbah Corps on social work education in Kano State was low. This finding relates with those of Faruque and Ahmmed (2013) in a study entitled *Development of Social Work Education and Practice in an Era of International Collaboration and Cooperation*. These scholars highlighted that the profession of social work places emphasis on cooperation through mutual interaction amongst individuals and communities. An increase in international cooperation in social work has expanded through research, mutual exchanges and discussion. The profession’s growing international commitment is evident through initiatives from NASW, ISWD, IFSW, IASSW, and CSWE. Social work is being challenged to rethink traditional paradigms of practice and education to meet interests of a complex, diverse, and divided world. Social work practitioners and educators must be willing to stop out of traditional models of practice and examine new ways of viewing theories, concepts, terms, beliefs, values, and policies in the profession to serve a more inclusive model of practice. Social work is at a crossroad of assuming a world-wide and environmental focus to address social problems based on an interdependent economy that is globally driven. However, the interview with clients of the Hisbah in Kano State extends that:

“Few of corps members are aware about schools that offer social work programmes of training, most of them place emphasis on traditional methods inculcated as a result of socialisation passed-over from generation to generation.”

The future of social work education requires an understanding of the broader context within which such education occurs. Social work can be conceived as located at the interface between the university and the society, with a range of multifaceted connections in specialisations. The interface with society occurs at a variety of levels within multiple sectors, including government organizations and community agencies.

Structural and demographic changes affect all of these sectors simultaneously, thereby generating demands for previously unforeseen services (Shera and Bogo, 2014).

Complement to the above findings is the finding of this study on the level of awareness on professional social work practice among the Hisbah Corps in Kano State. The finding revealed that; the awareness of the Hisbah Corps on professional social work practice in Kano State was low. The clients interviewed confirmed that:

“Corps members lacks awareness on the professional conduct of social work practice. They were unable to demonstrate the ethical principles such as formal training, registration with professional association and strict adherence of confidentiality of clients’ problems. Clients reported mal-treatment and repudiate the right and privileges of clients.”

According to Zastrow (2004) social work profession grew out of humanitarian and democratic ideals, and its values are based on respect for the equality, worth, and dignity of all people. Social workers are professionals who help support and protect people who are vulnerable and at risk. They work with people who are experiencing social and emotional problems and their families if they are affected. Social workers help people with day to day problems which affect their mental and physical well-being (Dubois and Miley, 2002).

The last finding of this study which revealed that the challenges faced by the Hisbah Corps in discharging their duties are interpreting and enforcing Sharia law within the framework of Nigeria's secular legal system; enforcing Islamic law and moral codes, which may not align with the views and beliefs of all residents; accusations of human rights abuses; enforcing conservative interpretations of Islamic morality; public opposition; inadequate funding; inadequate professional staffing; influenced by political leaders or factions, and collaboration and coordination with other law enforcement agencies in Kano State. The challenges of Hisbah reported during the interview with clients include:

“inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, inadequate office accommodation and facilities, inadequate transportation facilities, poor remuneration, inadequate trained and professional staff, conflict with national laws, interference of international human right organisations, and lack of educational qualification for further academic training among Corps members.”

In addition to this and in a study conducted by Abubakar and Abdallah, (2021) entitled “The Roles of Hisbah Commission and its Challenges in the Zamfara State of Nigeria”. The library research methodology was conducted specifically by collecting data from various written sources such as books, articles in scientific journals, research reports and even responsible daily newspapers. In addition, field studies, in an in-depth interview with relevant key figures were also conducted to strengthen the data obtained from the literature review. The results show that there are four main challenges in the implementation of Hisbah in Zamfara state, which are legal conflicts, lack of coordination of duties with the police force, negative public perception and lack of funds.

Conclusion

It is however observed from this study that the traditional, in other words conservative social work practice is currently the dominant trend undertaken by the Hisbah Board in Kano State. Yet, the empirical analysis in this study justified that most Corps members of Hisbah lack awareness of the available social work education institutions in the state, the region and Nigeria at large. There is also poor knowledge of professionalism among the Corps members in Kano. This is because of their inability to comply with the international standard of social work profession. Major issues of concern include among others registration with professional bodies for social work education and/or practice, code of conduct, training programmes, etc. In addition to this, the study discovered that the recruitment of the Corps members was on the basis of Islamic background, voluntary and political interference.

This study therefore has implication for reform in the policy that established the Hisbah Board in Kano State. In the sense that, within the polytechnics and universities in the North-west there are institutions that offer social work and social welfare programmes aimed at strengthening the knowledge of practice of social work

in our contemporaries. These formal programmes provides adequate knowledge of the application of the conventional social work practice globally.

Recommendations

From the above conclusions, therefore, the following recommendations are offered:

- i. Kano State government should reform the policy that established Hisbah in the State and mandate the office of the Head of Civil Service to recruit graduates from social work and welfare institutions to work as Hisbah corps in Kano State.
- ii. The institutions offering social work and welfare programmes should provide mobilization, enlightenment and training workshops for Hisbah corps members that will provide the awareness on social work education and professionalisation periodically.
- iii. The Hisbah Board should embark upon sensitisation exercise that will ginger the participation of individual philanthropists, NGOs, FBO, CSO and private institutions to provide resources meant for the services of the Hisbah Board in the State.

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